

DETERMINATION OF ANISOTROPIC ELASTIC PARAMETERS FROM HETEROGENEOUS STRAIN FIELDS

M. GREDIAC, A. VAUTRIN

Materials and Mechanical Engineering Department
Ecole des Mines de Saint-Etienne
158 cours Fauriel
42023 ST ETIENNE CEDEX 2, FRANCE

ABSTRACT

This paper describes the main features of a new approach of mechanical tests on anisotropic plates based on the measurement and processing of displacement fields. The main improvement of this approach is to show that one can directly measure and optimize the whole set of elastic properties involved in an anisotropic constitutive law through mechanical tests carried out on only one plate specimen. Moreover, parasitic effects which usually occur during tests on anisotropic specimens are avoided. This approach is based on the ability to solve the following inverse problem : how to determine material parameters from heterogeneous strain fields measured on the whole surface of the tested specimen ? Several examples of plate characterization show the relevance of this method in practice.

Keywords : bending tests, anisotropic plates, field measurements, invariants

1. INTRODUCTION

Anisotropic plates like long fiber composite material stacking sequences are structural components. Characterizing the parameters that govern the mechanical response of such structures is difficult because of their anisotropy and their heterogeneity. Complex stress fields take place in the specimen for most of the usual mechanical tests performed on composites. As a result, usual experimental data processings are not suitable for tests carried out on such structures and precautions must be taken for testing properly composite materials and structures.

An alternative of usual testing approaches is to consider directly that mechanical tests will give heterogeneous stress and strain fields and to take this feature into account in the data treatment. If one can determine material parameters from strain fields that are heterogeneous and analytically unknown, that will provide to the test designer with a real opportunity to define new mechanical tests well-suited to the particular response of composite materials and structures. For instance, it will be possible to determine the elastic parameters of an anisotropic plate from only one specimen in order to reduce the usual scatter due to the cutting of the samples. Moreover, it will be possible to define new sample geometries that allow several measurements in many directions in order to improve the number of experimental data in different directions. Hence, the identified mechanical

response of the sample will be optimized, and the knowledge into the material properties will therefore be improved.

2. ANALYSIS

2.1. The measurement of anisotropic material constants as an inverse problem in mechanics of structures

The challenge is here to measure stiffnesses or compliances from mechanical configurations that give heterogeneous strain fields. It can be defined as an inverse problem in mechanics of structures which is usually solved through mixed numerical/experimental approaches (see Figure 1) ([1], [2] for instance).

a- inverse problem : the displacement or strain fields are known, the forces and the geometry are known, the stress field is analytically unknown. How to determine the anisotropic material parameters ?

b- finite element simulation of the testing configuration.

Figure 1.

Assume the displacement field is known (the strain field would also be known by derivation), the usual procedure is to collect the displacement on the surface of the tested specimen. This set of data is then compared with that given by a finite element program (Figure 1-b). The goal is to obtain two sets of data which are identical. This is usually obtained using the following procedure (Figure 2).

Initial values of the parameters which are often close to the actual ones are required. The parameters are therefore not completely unknown. The difference between experimental and numerical results is computed with a deviation function, which must be minimized with respect to the parameters to be identified, using for example the gradient method [1] or a sensitivity analysis [2]. Finally, many finite element computations are required and the identified parameters are the last one used for the calculation.

Note that the Iosipescu shear test [3] is an interesting particular case, for which the shear strain field is heterogeneous. Moreover, only one measurement is made at the middle point of the sample. The measured shear strain is then related to the shear modulus using a correcting factor determined with finite element calculations. However, the iterative method in Figure 2 is avoided because the correcting factor has been previously established for several types of materials. The procedure is therefore more simple.

The approach proposed in the present paper is based on a direct calculation of the unknown parameters using an original treatment of the displacement field on the surface of the sample. It is based on the global equilibrium of the tested specimen using the principle of virtual work.

Figure 2. Mixed experimental/numerical procedures

Direct relationships involving the unknown parameters and the displacement field can be established [4], [5]. Consider for example a plate of any shape given (Figure 1-a), where the strain or the displacement field is known while the stress field is unknown. Applying the principle of virtual work with a compatible virtual displacement field Figure 3-a), one can write that the internal and external virtual work are equal for any virtual displacement field :

$$W^*_{int} = W^*_{ext} \quad (1)$$

with

$$W^*_{int} = \int_V \sigma_{ij} \varepsilon^*_{ij} dv = C_{ijkl} \int_V \varepsilon_{kl} \varepsilon^*_{ij} dv \quad (2)$$

and

$$W^*_{ext} = F_1 u^*_1 + F_2 u^*_2 \quad (3)$$

where V is the volume of the structure.

Integrating W^*_{int} by parts

$$F_1 u^*_1 + F_2 u^*_2 = \frac{1}{2} C_{ijkl} \left[\int_{\partial V} \varepsilon^*_{ij} (u_k \cos(n, x_l) + u_l \cos(n, x_k)) ds - \int_V \varepsilon^*_{ij,j} (u_k + u_l) dv \right] \quad (4)$$

One can therefore obtain one linear equation where the stiffnesses C_{ijkl} are unknown. Independent virtual fields provide as many linear equations as required to identify these unknowns. It can be observed that virtual strain fields which derivatives are zero only provide boundary integrals, which are in fact directly related to the average of the strain over the structure [5]. For instance, consider a virtual field with a constant virtual shear strain as shown in Figure 3-a for a plane structure. In this case, only the shear stiffness (and the shear coupling stiffnesses out of the eventual orthotropy axes) is involved in Equation 4. It can therefore be identified from the measured displacements on the boundary computing the boundary integral in Equation (4), as shown in Figure 3-b.

Figure 3. Virtual displacement of the structure.

2-2- An important consequence : the design at best of the tested sample geometry to obtain redundant data

Equation (4) is verified for any sample geometry. Consequently, one can define a geometry well-suited to the problem of the measurement of anisotropic stiffnesses or compliances. Assume the loading of the plate has been designed, one can then perform the experiments on a circular sample. This particular shape will allow a rotation of the sample in the mechanical set-up and will therefore give a set of identified parameters in any frame. As a result, one can optimize the mechanical response of the tested plate from experiments carried out on only one plate sample.

3- Example : the determination of the six independent bending compliances of composite plates from only one plate specimen

3-1- Introduction

The objective is here to measure the six independent bending compliances of several composite plates using static bending tests on plates. These compliances are involved in the relationship between the curvatures and the bending moments in the plate [6].

$$\begin{pmatrix} k_1 \\ k_2 \\ k_6 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} d_{11} & d_{12} & d_{16} \\ d_{12} & d_{22} & d_{26} \\ d_{16} & d_{26} & d_{66} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} M_1 \\ M_2 \\ M_6 \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

It is often more convenient to introduce the normalized compliances, which depend on the thickness h of the laminate:

$$d^*_{ij} = d_{ij} \frac{h^3}{12} \quad (6)$$

It must be pointed out that only a few loading and geometry cases provide an exact solution for the deflection [7]. The equation of equilibrium can actually be integrated only if the curvatures are constant. These latter cases cannot simply be obtained from a practical point of view, apart from the anticlastic configuration, used by Tsai [8] to measure the shear modulus. As a results, most of the configurations provide heterogeneous strain fields that are analytically unknown.

The procedure for heterogeneous strain fields treatment described above has been applied for solving this problem. It has led to the following experimental procedure which allows the characterization of anisotropic plates in bending.

3-2- Two basic bending tests for the composite plates

The above method has been applied to the determination of the bending properties of anisotropic plates. A mechanical configuration that provides heterogeneous strain fields where the six unknown parameters are involved leads to accurate results when using at least six independent virtual fields [4]. However, from a practical point of view, only three independent virtual fields that lead to constant virtual curvatures have been used for the experiments. Consequently, at least two bending tests are required to measure the six unknown parameters. It has been shown that the two tests in Figure 4 allow the direct determination of the six bending compliances computing boundary integrals that involve the displacements on the surface of the tested plates [5].

Figure 4. Two basic test used for the plate characterization

The first test is very similar to the anticlastic or torsion test usually carried out on square plates, for which the curvatures are constant. However, in the present case, the curvatures are heterogeneous and analytically unknown because of the circular shape of the sample. This test emphasizes the contribution of the torsional properties of the plate. The second test is very similar to the three point bending test usually carried out on beams. It mainly emphasizes the contribution of the compliance along direction x.

As explained above, the six unknown compliances are directly related to the displacements along the boundary of the plate. For instance, the compliance d_{11} is determined from the three point bending test using the following integral [5]:

$$d_{11} = - \frac{2}{FR} \int_0^{2\pi} w_{,x} \cos\theta \, d\theta \quad (7)$$

where $w_{,x}$ is the slope in direction x for points located along the boundary of the plate. This slope is the first derivative about x of the deflection w. It is directly related to the displacement on the

surface of the plate in direction x under the Love-Kirchhoff assumption. From a practical point of view, the slope contour is given by an optical moiré device. The moiré pattern is taken by a camera and digitized by a personal computer. The displacements along the boundary are then directly taken with a mouse on the screen of the computer. Integral in equation (7) is finally easily computed with these data. The other unknown compliances are computed through similar integrals. Full details can be found in [5].

Figure 5 shows a moiré pattern obtained with the three point bending test carried out on a 150 mm diameter plate specimen. As may be seen, the fringes, which are in fact constant value lines of the slope $w_{,x}$, are neither straight lines nor equidistant. Hence, the strain field is heterogeneous. It must be pointed out that only the displacements located along the boundary of the plate are taken into account when using virtual deflection fields with constant virtual curvatures. The whole field would be necessary for any other field. For simplicity reason, this approach has not been used in the present work.

Figure 5. Example of moiré pattern obtained with the three point bending test carried out in a off axis direction of an orthotropic plate

3-3- The use of invariants for the data treatment

One of the main features of the present approach is to provide the whole set of six compliances in any frame of the tested plate thanks to the ability to rotate the plate in the mechanical device. Hence, an important set of redundant data is obtained and must be averaged. The approach which has been used is to consider the tensorial nature of the measured compliances and to introduce the invariants of the compliance tensor. The main advantage of such quantities is to be intrinsic, i. e. independent on direction of orientation. As a result, a graphical representation of the experimental data can be given in the complex plane and one can easily define Mohr's circles that fit at best these experimental data. The optimized elastic response of the anisotropic plate is finally represented by two Mohr's circles, from which the compliances can be computed in any coordinates system [6], [9], [10]. This averaging procedure is presented in [10]. The main interest is to give a compact representation of the results, to measure the experimental scatter and finally to average the experimental data using intrinsic tools.

3-4- Results

Several plates have been tested with the above procedure. All of them are 150 mm diameter and have been cut directly in the laminated plates to be identified. These six compliances have been measured in 7 different frame rotated through 15 deg one from another. Figures 6 and 7 show three examples of results. The first plate is a $[0,90]_{6S}$ carbon/epoxy stacking sequence. The bending properties of this laminate present almost a square symmetry. Consequently, one of the two Mohr's circles reduces to a point in the complex plane [10]. This property clearly appears in

Figure 6. The six independent normalized compliances measured in ten different frames are compactly represented in this figure. Circles obtained from the estimated compliances computed within the classical laminated plate theory (CLPT) [6] are also reported and are in agreement with experimental data.

Figure 6. Generalized Mohr's circles for a $[0,90]_{6s}$ carbon/epoxy stacking sequence.

Figure 7. Generalized Mohr's circles for two $[0_n,45_n,90_n,135_n]_s$ carbon/epoxy stacking sequences, $n=2$ and $n=3$.

The two other plates have been cut respectively in two stacking sequences $[0_n,45_n,90_n,135_n]_s$, with $n=2$ and $n=3$. In-plane elastic properties of both plates are isotropic. On the other hand, their

bending elastic properties are completely anisotropic. It must be emphasized that these two plates have theoretically the same normalized compliances. Experimental points obtained with those two plates are reported in Figure 7. It clearly appears that the two set of circles are different. The mechanical response of the two plates is therefore different in terms of reduced compliances. This discrepancy is certainly due to the manufacturing process, that induces a scatter in the final properties of laminated plates. Circles obtained within the framework of the classical laminated plate theory are also reported and are not in so good agreement as for the first example.

Conclusion

A new approach allowing the global determination of anisotropic elastic parameters is presented in this paper. The globality of the material behaviour is guaranteed through the fact that the mean value of the strain of the whole specimen surface was measured and the whole strain field has therefore been taken into account.

The present procedure departs from the usual approach used for laminate elastic parameters measurements, for which the goal is to obtain homogeneous strain fields and to consider several specimens. In the present paper, it has been shown that a heterogeneous strain distribution may contain enough informations to perform redundant measurements on a single specimen. Hence, the identification of mechanical parameters directly on parts of structures through relevant strain or displacement fields treatments seems to be a promising issue in composite material characterization.

References

1. Foudjet, A., Duhau, R., Surry C. and J. F. Jullien, 1981, "*Identification of elastic constants of wood*", Proceedings of the International Symposium on the Mechanical Behaviour of Structured Media. Ottawa, pp. 463-477.
2. Hendriks, M., 1991, "*Identification of the mechanical behavior of solid materials*", doctoral dissertation, Technische Universiteit Eindhoven, the Netherland.
3. Morton, J., Ho, H., Tsai, M. Y. and Farley, G. L., 1992, "*An evaluation of the Iosipescu specimen for composite materials shear property measurement*", Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 27, pp. 708-750.
4. Grédiac, M. and A. Vautrin, 1990, "*A new method for determination of bending rigidities of thin anisotropic plates*", Journal of Applied Mechanics, Transaction of the ASME, Vol. 57, pp. 964-968.
5. Grédiac, M. and A. Vautrin, 1993, "*Mechanical characterization of anisotropic plates, experiments and results*", accepted for publication in the European Journal of Mechanics. A/Solids.
6. Tsai, S. W. and H. T. Hahn, 1980, *Introduction to composite materials*, Technomic, Publishing Co. Inc., Westport, Connecticut.
7. Lekhnitskii S. G., 1968, *Anisotropic Plates*, Gordon and Breach, Science Publishers inc. New York.
8. Tsai S. W., 1965, "*Experimental determination of the elastic behavior of orthotropic plates*", Journal for Engineering in Industry, Transaction of the ASME, pp. 315-318.
9. Kandil, N. and G. Verchery, 1989, "*Some new developments in the design of stacking sequences of laminates*", Proceedings of the ICCM 7, Beijing, Pergamon Press, Vol. 3, pp. 358-363.
10. Grédiac, M., Vautrin A. and G. Verchery, 1993, "*A general method for data averaging of anisotropic elastic constants*", accepted for publication in the Journal of Applied Mechanics, Transaction of the ASME.